

Polymetallic complexes. Part-LXXXIII : $O^{\wedge}O^{\wedge}N^{\wedge}O$ and $O^{\wedge}O^{\wedge}N$ donor azodye dimeric complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}

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Abstract : Twelve dinuclear complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with one tetradentate $O^{\wedge}O^{\wedge}N^{\wedge}O$ donor azodye ligand (LH_3), 3-(2'-hydroxynaphthyl-4'-sulphonic acid azo)-2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoic acid (HNSAHCB) and one tridentate $O^{\wedge}O^{\wedge}N$ donor azodye ligand ($L'H_2$), 3-(naphthyl azo)-2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoic acid (NAHCB) have been prepared. The complexes have been characterized by analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, IR, electronic spectra, ESR, NMR and X-ray diffraction (powder pattern) data. The cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes are found to be octahedral. Copper(II) complexes are distorted octahedral and a tetrahedral stereochemistry has been assigned for Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes.

Keywords : Polydentate azodye ligands, polymetallic complexes.

Introduction

The azodyes exhibit both chemotherapeutic and anti-septic properties¹. Some of the azodyes are used for dyeing food stuffs, for preserving food grains and as redox indicator^{2,3}. Potentiometric and spectrophotometric studies of metal complexes containing azodye ligands have also been reported. Synthesis of inorganic polymers containing polydentate azodyes is of recent interest. We are synthesizing multidentate azodyes and their polymeric metal complexes⁴. The present paper reports the synthesis of two new multidentate azodyes containing oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms and their twelve dimeric metal complexes.

Results and discussion

The dimeric complexes synthesized have the compositions $[M_2LCl(H_2O)_6]$, $[M'_2LCl(H_2O)_2]$, $[M_2L'Cl_2(H_2O)_6]$ and $[M'_2L'Cl_2(H_2O)_2]$ where $M = Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} ; $M' = Zn^{II}$, Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} ; $LH_3 = 3$ -(2'-hydroxynaphthyl-4'-sulphonic acid azo)-2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoic acid (Fig. 1) and $L'H_2 = 3$ -(naphthyl azo)-2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoic acid (Fig. 2). All the twelve complexes have high melting points and are amorphous in nature and insoluble in common organic solvents like methanol, ethanol and benzene but feebly soluble in dioxane, DMF and DMSO. Low conductance values (5.2 – $6.5 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) of the complexes in DMF indicate the non-elec-

Fig. 1. $[LH_3]$ or (HNSAHCB).

Fig. 2. $L'H_2$ or (NAHCB).

trolytic nature of the complexes as the molar conductance of the complexes in DMF solution usually fall in the range 85 – 100 , 140 – 170 and 200 – $260 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ for 1 : 1, 2 : 1 and 3 : 1 electrolytes⁵.

In the IR spectra of the ligands, broad bands are ob-

served at 3552 cm⁻¹ (LH₃) and 3444 cm⁻¹ (L'H₂) which may be attributed to intramolecular O-H...N hydrogen bonding. These bands disappear in the metal chelates indicating the bonding of the phenolic -OH groups with the metal atoms. The bands at 1473 cm⁻¹ (LH₃) and 1499 cm⁻¹ (L'H₂) in the ligands can be ascribed to phenolic C-O vibration and in the metal chelates these bands appear at ~1463 cm⁻¹ indicating the bonding of the ligands to the metal ions through the phenolic oxygen atoms⁶. The sharp bands in the ligands appear at 1635 cm⁻¹ (LH₃) and at 1623 cm⁻¹ (L'H₂), which can be assigned to ν_{N=N} vibration and in the metal chelates these bands appear at ~1616 cm⁻¹ and at ~1602 cm⁻¹ respectively which indicates the bonding of the azo nitrogen atoms to the metal⁷. In the metal complexes broad bands appeared at ~3275 cm⁻¹ and at ~3273 cm⁻¹ followed by sharp peaks at ~842 cm⁻¹ and at ~815 cm⁻¹ assignable to OH stretching and rocking vibrations respectively indicating the presence of co-ordinated water molecules in the complexes⁸. The ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} bands in the complexes, appearing at ~532 cm⁻¹ and ~477 cm⁻¹ confirm the bonding of the ligands to the metal ions through oxygen and nitrogen atoms respectively⁹.

In the electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes, three ligand field bands are observed at 8158 (8172) cm⁻¹, 16320

(16410) cm⁻¹ and 20180 (20210) cm⁻¹ assignable to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F)(ν₁), → ⁴A_{2g}(F)(ν₂) and → ⁴T_{1g}(P)(ν₃) transitions respectively. The values of spectral parameters like Dq, B, β₃₅, ν₂/ν₁ and σ are found to be 816.2 (823.8) cm⁻¹, 801.73 (806.93) cm⁻¹, 0.825 (0.831) cm⁻¹, 2.006 (2.008) and 21.212 (20.336)% respectively, suggestive of an octahedral geometry for the complexes¹⁰. In the electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes, three ligand field bands are observed at 10220 (10242) cm⁻¹, 17145 (17155) cm⁻¹ and 24995 (24998) cm⁻¹ assignable to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F)(ν₁), → ³T_{1g}(F)(ν₂) and → ³T_{1g}(P)(ν₃) transitions respectively in an octahedral symmetry field. The ligand field parameters like Dq, B, β₃₅, ν₂/ν₁ and σ are found to be 1022.0 (1024.2) cm⁻¹, 760.93 (761.8) cm⁻¹, 0.730 (0.731) cm⁻¹, 1.677 (1.674) and 36.986 (36.798)% respectively in conformity with an octahedral geometry for the Ni^{II} complexes¹¹. In the electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes, one broad asymmetric band appears in 13535–14875 cm⁻¹ region with a maxima at ~14375 cm⁻¹ which could be attributed to ²E_g → ²T_{2g} transition in support of a distorted octahedral geometry of the complexes¹².

The complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} exhibit sub-normal magnetic moments (Table 1) and it can be attributed to the magnetic interaction between the metals present

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes

Sl. no.	Compd. (Molecular/Empirical formula)	Colour	μ _{eff} (B.M.)	λ _m (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
					Metal	N	S	Cl
1.	LH ₃ (HNSAHCB)	Reddish brown	-	-	-	6.3 (6.6)	7.2 (7.5)	8.2 (8.4)
2.	L'H ₂ (NAHCB)	Coffee	-	-	-	8.4 (8.5)	-	10.4 (10.8)
3.	[Co ₂ (HNSAHCB)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Pink	2.6	6.1	17.1 (17.3)	3.9 (4.1)	4.5 (4.7)	10.1 (10.4)
4.	[Co ₂ (NAHCB)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Pink	2.5	6.5	18.5 (18.9)	4.1 (4.5)	-	16.9 (17.1)
5.	[Ni ₂ (HNSAHCB)Cl(H ₂ O) ₆]	Green	2.3	5.8	17.0 (17.2)	3.8 (4.1)	4.3 (4.7)	10.1 (10.4)
6.	[Ni ₂ (NAHCB)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Yellow	2.2	5.2	18.6 (18.9)	4.2 (4.5)	-	16.8 (17.1)
7.	[Cu ₂ (HNSAHCB)Cl(H ₂ O) ₆]	Green	1.3	5.9	18.1 (18.4)	3.8 (4.0)	4.2 (4.6)	10.1 (10.2)
8.	[Cu ₂ (NAHCB)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Blue	1.2	6.4	19.8 (20.1)	4.2 (4.4)	-	16.5 (16.8)
9.	[Zn ₂ (HNSAHCB)Cl(H ₂ O) ₂]	Grey	Dia.	6.0	20.7 (21.0)	4.3 (4.5)	4.8 (5.1)	11.2 (11.4)

Table-1 (contd.)

10.	[Zn ₂ (NAHCB)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Reddish brown	Dia.	5.7	22.9	4.5	-	18.6
					(23.2)	(4.9)		(18.9)
11.	[Cd ₂ (HNSAHCB)Cl(H ₂ O) ₂]	White	Dia.	5.3	31.1	3.5	4.2	9.4
					(31.4)	(3.9)	(4.4)	(9.9)
12.	[Cd ₂ (NAHCB)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	Dia.	5.6	33.8	3.9	-	15.8
					(34.2)	(4.2)		(16.2)
13.	[Hg ₂ (HNSAHCB)Cl(H ₂ O) ₂]	White	Dia.	6.3	44.3	2.8	3.2	7.5
					(44.9)	(3.1)	(3.5)	(7.9)
14.	[Hg ₂ (NAHCB)Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Reddish brown	Dia.	5.4	47.8	3.1	-	12.5
					(48.2)	(3.3)		(12.7)

in a dimeric structure¹³ $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{M} \text{---} \text{O} \text{---} \text{M} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{O} \end{array} \right)$.

The ESR spectra of the complexes [Cu₂LCl(H₂O)₆] and [Cu₂L'Cl₂(H₂O)₆] have been recorded at X-band at RT. In the former complex 'g_{av}' is found to be 2.06436 by applying Kneubuhl's method¹⁴. This type of spectrum appears as a result of interaction between Cu-Cu ions in a dimeric or polymeric structure. Strong antiferromagnetic coupling is suggested for the complex through dimeric association which is further supported by the low magnetic moment data. In the later complex g₁, g₂ and g₃ values are found at 2.0273, 2.0996 and 2.2084 respectively. The axial symmetry parameter "G" for the complex is calculated to be 3.2 which indicates a strong exchange interaction among magnetically equivalent Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell. In order to obtain information about the ground state, another useful parameter "R" is calculated and is found to be < 1 (0.66) which indicates that

the ground state is predominantly d_{x²-y²}.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands LH₃ and L'H₂ were recorded in CDCl₃ solvent and TMS as internal standard. The complex pattern observed at δ 6.373-7.937 (LH₃) and at δ 6.670-7.937 (L'H₂) correspond to seven and nine phenyl protons respectively. The sharp peaks observed at δ 8.925 (LH₃) and at δ 8.573 (L'H₂) can be assigned to two and one phenolic protons respectively.

The XRD (powder pattern) of the complexes [Co₂LCl(H₂O)₆] and [Co₂L'Cl₂(H₂O)₆] have been indexed in X-ray diffractometer and the unit cell parameters have been calculated with the help of a computer from 2θ values (Figs. 3 and 4). The unit cell parameters like A, B, C, α, β, γ, V (volume) suggest the probable geometry of the former complex to be 'monoclinic' and the latter complex 'triclinic'(Table 2). The density of the complexes has been determined by the floatation method in a satu-

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffraction graph of the complex : [Co₂(HNSAHCB)Cl(H₂O)₆].

Note

Fig. 4. X-Ray diffraction graph of the complex : $[\text{Co}_2(\text{NAHCB})\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$.

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction data of the complexes

Compd.	2θ		Unit cell parameters	Density (g/cc)	n	Possible geometry
	values					
$[\text{Co}_2(\text{HNSAHCB})\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$	12.749	14.403	A = 9.508	0.942	1.0	Monoclinic
	15.556	22.096	B = 9.145			
	25.315	27.187	C = 8.507			
	30.479	31.649	α = 90.000			
	34.757	37.983	β = 102.387			
	38.668	42.678	γ = 90.000			
	44.065	46.405	V = 722.46			
	48.577	49.563				
	50.633	53.541				
	54.761	56.499				
58.320						
$[\text{Co}_2(\text{NAHCB})\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$	14.236	15.623	A = 9.037	1.493	2.0	Triclinic
	16.375	22.608	B = 12.557			
	24.814	25.382	C = 7.571			
	26.569	29.510	α = 98.615			
	31.766	33.069	β = 98.798			
	34.824	37.899	γ = 96.143			
	39.336	40.272	V = 832.01			
	42.879	43.798				
	43.932	45.987				
	46.756	48.394				
	50.666	51.452				
	53.006	53.507				
	55.780	57.000				
58.471						

rated solution of KBr, NaCl and benzene separately. The number of formula units per unit cell (n) is calculated

from the relation $n = dNV/M$, where d = density of the compound, N = Avogadro's number, V = volume of the

unit cell and M = molecular weight of the complex. The calculated value of ' n ' is 1.0 for the former complex and 2.0 for the latter complex and these values agree well with the suggested structure of the complex¹⁵.

The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are suggested to be four co-ordinated having a tetrahedral geometry based on analytical, conductance and IR spectral data. Hence the azodye LH_3 behaves as a tetradentate and $L'H_2$ as a tridentate ligand. Both the azodyes form dimeric complexes and dimerisation is achieved through phenolic oxygen bridge. The representative structures of the two series of complexes can be shown in Figs. 5 and 6 respectively.

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Experimental

All the chemicals were procured from B.D.H. or E. Merck and were used as received. Metal, nitrogen and chlorine were estimated by standard methods¹⁶. Conductivity measurement in DMF was done using Toshniwal CL 01-06 conductivity bridge. The magnetic moment was measured at room temperature by Gouy method. IR

spectra (KBr) were recorded using IFS 66U spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (10^{-2} M in DMF) using a Hilger-Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer, ESR spectra on a E_4 -spectrometer and NMR spectra on a Jeol GSX-400 in $CDCl_3$ as solvent and TMS as internal standard and X-ray diffraction (powder pattern) of the complexes have been recorded on a PW 1130/00 model X-ray diffractometer.

Preparation of the ligands :

The azodye ligands were synthesized by the coupling reaction of the diazonium chlorides obtained from l-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid (0.01 M, 2.39 g) and 2-naphthylamine (0.01 M, 1.43 g) with alkaline solution of 5-chloro-salicylic acid (0.01 mol, 1.72 g) at 0-5 °C.

Preparation of the complexes :

The metal chlorides in ethanol were reacted with ethanolic solution of the ligands in 2 : 1 molar ratio and the resulting solution was then heated at 50-60 °C for about 1 h on a heating mantle. On cooling, pH of the solution was raised to ~7 by adding conc. ammonia drop by drop with stirring. The solid complexes, thus separated were then washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

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